

**UNSTEADY INGESTION AND JET FILM COOLING CHARACTERISTICS IN TURBINE
MULTI-GAP ENDWALL UNDER UPSTREAM WAKE INFLUENCE**

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ABSTRACT

For the essential multi-gap cooling structures on typical turbine endwalls, the periodic upstream wake passing can cause severe gap ingestion fluctuation and uniform outflow. The conventional gap layout design under uniform inflow condition can lead to periodic endwall cooling failure. This paper employs the unsteady RANS method to numerically investigate the coupled mechanism of the unsteady secondary flow, gap ingestion and endwall cooling performances under wake passing. During the movement of upstream wake moves from leading edge to pressure side, the slot ejection on pressure side is substantially strengthened to enlarge the coverage on endwall, causing the highest averaging cooling effectiveness. However, the ingestion is the severest at slashface middle part. The slot coolant leakage has the largest coverage length on suction side endwall when the wake passing the mid-pitch location, minimizing the influence of suction side horseshoe vortex on pressure side. The slot coolant tends to penetrate into the mainstream instead of reattaching on endwall when the wake is aligned with the suction side, resulting in an average endwall cooling effectiveness approximately 0.1-0.2 lower than when the wake is aligned with the pressure side. The total pressure loss coefficient at the exit first decreases and then increases, reaching its minimum value when the wake is aligned with the mid-pitch location. Thus, advanced endwall cooling layout designs should consider the typical turbine unsteady flow effects such as wake flow to enhance turbine cooling performance robustness and weaken the unsteady gap ingestion strength for higher operation safety.

Keywords: Gas turbine; Wake flow; Endwall gap; Film cooling

1. INTRODUCTION

Gas Turbines operate in high-temperature environments far exceeding material melting points, posing challenges for turbine hot component cooling protection, Film cooling is the

most commonly used cooling technology^[1-3] in turbine cascades, including the vane and endwall components. The endwall is one of the most challenging components which need strict protection. The strong secondary flow characteristics within the endwall region can easily lead to erosion of hotspots.

Typically, the design of film cooling is conducted under design conditions^[4]. However, various unsteady phenomena exist during turbine operation, including mainstream fluctuations, periodic wake effects, and periodically shed secondary flow, causing instantaneous film cooling failure, overheating and burnout issues. With increasingly demanding performance for advanced gas turbines, research on unsteady film cooling effects for has gradually gained attention to ensure the robustness of cooling performance throughout entire cycle. Qenawy et al.^[5] used the pressure sensitive paint technique to capture the unsteady film cooling behaviors behind shaped holes. The unsteadiness is mainly controlled by the vortical structures originated from hole entrance. Choi et al.^[6] used a rob to mimic the upstream wake of a turbine cascade, and the its influence on endwall unsteady heat transfer performance is measured by naphthalene simulation method. The meeting position of the passage vortex and wake flow largely influence the endwall heat transfer behavior. Yang et al.^[7] numerically investigate the unsteady heat transfer performance of endwall by considering realistic mainstream inlet profile. Zhang et al.^[8] experimentally measured the influence of upstream film coolant on endwall by considering the unstable boundary layer formed by steps. Zhou et al.^[9] used the high-speed camera to measure the unsteady flow characteristics of film holes jets from leading edge with different hole geometries. The fan-shaped and transverse-trenched can both improve the cooling uniformity by generate low-momentum coolants. Fawcett et al.^[10] used the high-speed camera to measure the influence of crossflow on coolant ejection unsteadiness on

vane surface, and two unsteady structures of hairpin vortices and shear layer vortices are observed.

The turbine component of endwall features two inherent gap structures, separately referred to as slot and slashface^[11], both serving as primary film cooling structures for endwall. The slot is the gap between stators and rotors, while the slashface is the assembly gap between adjacent blade pieces. The mainstream flows above these gaps, while the secondary air system lies beneath, making them interfaces between turbine cascade and secondary air system. Generally, rim seals are employed for slots, and cloth seals for slashfaces, to mitigate mainstream ingestion and prevent safety issues such as burnout within the secondary air system^[12]. Zhang et al.^[13] used the pressure sensitive paint method to measure the film cooling performance of a convex endwall with upstream slot jet. The decreasing of slot inclination angle can weaken the secondary flow. Feng et al.^[14] modeled the upstream slot as vane shape and cascade shape, and their cooling effectiveness on turbine endwall is simulated. Two shaped slots lead to higher cooling effectiveness compared with the traditional slot. Shaikh et al.^[15] built a low-order model to predict the aerodynamic loss and heat transfer strength caused by endwall mid-passage gap leakage. Zhang et al.^[16] simulated the non-uniform slashface leakage flow on turbine endwall, and the slashface cooling structure with different inclination angles are compared.

Based on the steady flow characteristic investigations of the turbine slot leakages, considerable researches^[17] have also been conducted on unsteady ingestion phenomena for slots and disk cavities. Lin et al.^[18] used the numerical method to investigate the flow and heat transfer characteristics considering different Mach numbers in a rotating disk cavity, and experimental and theoretical methods are also conducted for validation. The results show that the disk wall Nusselt number is enhanced to 1639.4 and 1286.9 with the increase of flowing Mach number from 0.006 to 0.15. Beaux et al.^[19] conducted a numerical work to predict the ingress and heat transfer in a 2-stage turbine disk cavity. Du et al.^[20] used the detached eddy simulation to investigate the film cooling performance of the endwall upstream interrupted slot along with its unsteady flow jet behavior. The simulations reveal that the horseshoe vortex formation is dominated by the shedding vortices, and their coupling effect has a large influence on the film cooling distribution on the endwall. Lopes et al.^[21] experimentally measured the unsteady performance of the cascade aerodynamic parameters caused by the slot injection and upstream weak flow. The slot injection increases the loss fluctuation by 178%. Liu et al.^[22] numerically simulated the steady endwall cooling characteristics with pulsed slot leakage with different forms, and the form of square wave shows the worst cooling effect.

However, fewer unsteady studies exist for slashface^[23], resulting in fluctuations of ingestion and overheat within

slashface. The film cooling performance of slashface jets also frequently deviates from design values. The slot leakage significantly impacts slashface ingestion, with complex interactions between coolant jets from two endwall gaps and secondary vortices in the endwall region. Similarly, unsteady flows within turbine cascades cause significant changes in gap jet patterns and secondary flow structures, thereby affecting unsteady aerodynamic and cooling performance in the cascade endwall region.

Upstream wake is among the primary cause of periodic pressure fluctuations in downstream cascades, resulting in variations in unsteady mainstream ingestion and coolant outflow at endwall^[24-25]. This paper employs the unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) methods to investigate the unsteady ingestion and coolant outflow characteristics of turbine endwall gaps under the influence of upstream vane wakes. The unsteady film cooling effects of non-uniform gap jets on endwall and the unsteady development of secondary flows are studied, providing technical support for more robust aerodynamic and heat transfer designs of multi-gap turbine endwall.

2. NUMERICAL METHODS

2.1 Geometrical model and boundary conditions

In order to investigate the effects of the periodic process of upstream wake movement on unsteady secondary flows and variations in cooling performance on turbine cascade endwall, this study employs a turbine blade cascade equipped with a multi-cavity endwall cooling system, including slot and slashface cooling structures, as the research object. A schematic diagram of the cascade model is presented in Fig. 1(a). The profile of the blade and the cascade are derived from a cascade wind tunnel experiment^[26], adopting identical geometric parameters and boundary conditions to those used in the experimental study, thereby enabling validation of the numerical results against experimental data. The blade is scaled from an actual gas turbine rotor blade. To more clearly examine the ejection and interaction characteristics inherent to the two gap structures on the endwall, no film cooling holes were configured on the endwall surface. This study employs a computational domain covering one circumferential periodic segment of the turbine cascade to numerically evaluate the cooling performance of the endwall. The key geometric parameters of the cascade are summarized in Table 1. In this paper, the leading edge of the blade is defined as the position $z=0$.

Table 1 Cascade geometry parameters

Parameters	Values / mm
Span	126.4
Chord length	89.7
Pitch	77.14
Axial chord length	81.63

The slot gap refers to the rim seal outlet between the stator and the rotor. Typically, the coolant from the slot undergoes pre-swirl within the disc cavity, allowing it to attain a discharge angle nearly identical to that of the mainstream flow. In this study, the velocity components of the coolant jet are specified to align with the incident angle of the mainstream flow. The slot is positioned at $0.073C_{ax}$ upstream of leading edge, with a discharge angle of 25° and a width of 2 mm.

consistent with the assembly configuration of typical blade pieces, the slashface employs a typical vertical gap, covering the endwall region from 0.1 to 1.1 C_{ax} in the axial direction. Thirty uniformly distributed coolant injection holes are used to simulate the discontinuous coolant leakage from cloth seal under slashface. The depth and length of the slashface are 4.3 mm and 1.6 mm, respectively. The inner wall of the slashface gap is set as smooth surface. The slashface and the slot are supplied with coolant by separate underlying coolant chambers.

During numerical calculation of endwall cooling performance, the slot remains an ejection mass flow ratio of 1.0%, while the blowing ratio of the slashface leakage is 1.0. The blowing ratio (M) is defined as:

$$M = \frac{\rho_c V_c}{\rho_\infty V_\infty} \quad (1)$$

where V and ρ are the fluid velocity and density, c and ∞ separately represent coolant and mainstream fluid.

The pressure ratio across the cascade inlet and outlet in simulations is consistent with that in blow-down tests, with the inlet and outlet Mach numbers being 0.28 and 0.45, respectively. Both the mainstream and the coolant are treated as ideal gases. To investigate the influence of upstream wake movement effects, the cascade incorporates inlet boundary conditions that include the upstream vane wake region, where pressure (P), temperature (T) have periodic unsteady variations along pitchwise direction. Similar to the upstream slot, the temperature and pressure profiles at the upstream wake cross-section are obtained from the interface between the turbine stators and rotors. The P and T in the wake region are set at 95% and 98% of the mainstream values, respectively. It's verified that the periodic variations of wake flow with time can be characterized by the following sinusoidal functions^[27]:

$$P(t, \theta) = P_m (1 - 5\% \sin(n\theta / 2 + \pi t / \tau))^{10} \quad (2)$$

$$T(t, \theta) = T_m (1 - 2\% \sin(n\theta / 2 + \pi t / \tau))^{10} \quad (3)$$

where τ is the time period of the wake flow.

Since the turbulence intensity in the wake region is significantly higher compared to the mainstream region, the following functions are used to characterize the turbulence intensity and characteristic length distribution at cascade inlet:

$$Tu(t, \theta) = Tu_m (1 + 50\% \sin(n\theta / 2 + \pi t / \tau))^6 \quad (4)$$

$$L(t, \theta) = L_m (1 + 150\% \sin(n\theta / 2 + \pi t / \tau))^6 \quad (5)$$

In this study, the numerical simulation of the periodically moving upstream wake is conducted with the zero-time reference defined as the moment when the wake is aligned with the blade leading edge. The relative positioning between the wake and the cascade during the process is as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 Correspondence between time steps and wake positions

Time steps	Weak position
T_0	Leading edge
$T_0+1/4\tau$	Pressure side
$T_0+2/4\tau$	Mid-pitch
$T_0+3/4\tau$	Suction side

2.1 Mesh and calculation method

The structured mesh of the cascade with boundary layers near the endwall and blade surfaces is generated by software ICEM CFD. Fig. 2 presents a schematic diagram of the mesh for the cascade and cooling structure. The mesh is refined around the slot surface, slashface wall surface, endwall and blade surfaces to maintain high-quality boundary layer meshes, and their y^+ is varied based on different turbulence model types. The mesh for the cascade and the slashface structure are generated separately and connected via a general interface. A grid independence study was conducted using meshes with node numbers of 5.7 million, 7.1 million, 11.0 million, 12.4 million, and 18.9 million, respectively. The results indicate that increasing the total number of nodes beyond 12.4 million does not significantly improve computational accuracy, while simultaneously maintaining a balance with computational efficiency.

FIGURE 2: Structured mesh of the cascade endwall and cooling layouts

The numerical simulations of the transient slashface ingestion and endwall cooling phenomena used the ANSYS CFX software with unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) method. The second-order backward Euler scheme was implemented for temporal discretization. To determine the appropriate time step size for the unsteady numerical simulations, time steps ranging from $1/10\tau$ to $1/800\tau$ were selected and tested in the unsteady calculations. With the averaging cooling effectiveness of the endwall serving as the evaluation criterion, it was observed that when the time step was decreased to below $1/300\tau$, the computations sufficiently resolved the unsteady effects of the upstream wake flow and the film cooling within the endwall region. Therefore, a time step size of $1/300\tau$ was adopted for the transient simulations in this study. The maximum coefficient loops during simulations were set as 5.

To evaluate the cooling performance of the gap coolant leakages on turbine endwall, two parameters of the non-dimensional temperature (θ) of the fluid and the cooling effectiveness (η) of the wall surface are separately defined as:

$$\eta = \frac{T_{\infty} - T_{aw}}{T_{\infty} - T_c} \quad (6)$$

$$\theta = \frac{T - T_c}{T_{\infty} - T_c} \quad (7)$$

where aw represents the adiabatic endwall condition, and T is the temperature.

FIGURE 3: Numerical validation results of endwall cooling effectiveness contours by experiment data

Based on the wind tunnel experiment data of the endwall cooling performance [26], the numerical method for calculating the flow and cooling performance within the endwall region under the influence of upstream wake flow movement is validated as shown in Fig. 3. To more accurately predict near-

endwall coolant flow and heat transfer, the above defined boundary layers of pressure, temperature, etc. are incorporated at the cascade inlet during calculation. By comparing the prediction results of endwall cooling distribution by five different turbulence models, the SST $k-\omega$ model achieves the best prediction of the slot coolant coverage on endwall, especially around blade leading edge. For the slashface leakage coverage, three $k-\omega$ models have better prediction, including the wedge-shaped coverage on middle part endwall and the small coverage near slashface trailing edge. Thus, the SST $k-\omega$ model was adopted after a turbulence model validation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 presents the typical endwall cooling effectiveness distribution and secondary flow system in the endwall region under coolant leakages of slot and slashface with uniform inflow. Similar to the secondary flow structures in typical cascades, under the combined effects of spanwise and streamwise pressure gradients at the blade leading edge, the horseshoe vortex (HV) is generated in the leading edge corner region, with its two branches flowing toward pressure side and suction side separately. The horseshoe vortex constitutes one of the primary factors affecting the flow uniformity in the upstream endwall region. Additionally, when develops toward downstream, the slot coolant leakage also induces the formation of the separation vortex (SV). Due to the proximity of the slot to the horseshoe vortex generation location, the slot coolant jet is significantly influenced by the horseshoe vortex. The pressure side and suction side HV branches possess opposite rotational directions, which consequently entrain the slot coolant into the wedge-shaped area and confine the coolant within the wedge-shaped area on suction side endwall.

Under uniform inflow condition, the slashface coolant jet forms a wedge-shaped coverage area on suction side endwall, which results from the spread of the middle part slashface coolant outflow under the influence of the lateral pressure gradient within the endwall region. The upstream part slashface coolant outflow is significantly affected by the horseshoe vortex above, with the pressure side HV crossing over the slashface from upstream or middle part regions and exerting substantial influence on its reattachment strength on downstream part endwall. Simultaneously, under the entrainment effect of the horseshoe vortex, the slot coolant exhibits certain ingestion phenomena into the slashface, particularly in the upstream part of the slashface. In contrast, the downstream part slashface coolant outflow experiences minimal influence from secondary flows. The coolant outflow rate in the downstream part slashface is significantly higher than that in the upstream part, and the high-velocity coolant outflow near the slashface trailing edge renders it difficult to attach to the endwall.

FIGURE 4: Cooling effectiveness and vorticity distributions in endwall region

Figure 5 illustrates the variations in endwall cooling effectiveness during wake sweeping across a cascade period. Compared to uniform inflow, the circumferential movement of wake flow causes significant changes in the reattachment range of the gap coolant leakages on the endwall.

When the wake passes through the leading edge, the slot coolant forms a protrusion on pressure side endwall. This occurs because the slot coolant, which previously had difficulty flowing out from this region, can now exit the slot due to the decreased pressure in the low-pressure region of the weak flow. Simultaneously, the coolant ejection from the upstream pressure side slot can affect the pressure side endwall, resulting in a slight improvement in the cooling effectiveness on pressure side endwall compared to uniform inflow (in Fig. 4). The suction-side slot coolant, being unaffected by the wake flow, exhibits no significant difference in coverage compared to uniform inflow. Different from the relatively uniform slashface coolant coverage observed under uniform inflow, the slashface coolant tends to cover the middle part of the endwall with an increased coverage width, while the coolant coverage near the slashface leading and trailing edges remains relatively unchanged.

When the wake flows across the pressure-side endwall, there is a significant increase in the cooling coverage area on the pressure side endwall compared to the minimal cooling observed with uniform inflow. This enhancement is attributed to the substantial increase in coolant outflow from slot pressure side. The pressure side slot coolant spreads to the downstream region of the pressure side endwall, as the slot leakage overcomes the constraints imposed by the pressure side horseshoe vortex, significantly improving the cooling effectiveness of the pressure side endwall compared to uniform inflow condition. The increased coolant outflow from the upstream part slashface enables coolant coverage in the region between slot and slashface, while the downstream slashface coolant coverage shifts slightly downstream compared to uniform inflow condition.

When the wake passes through the mid-pitch location, the coolant coverage length on suction side endwall increases significantly due to enhanced coolant outflow from the middle part slot, which is entrained by the suction side HV and reattaches to the endwall near the suction side corner region. The slashface coolant coverage area remains similar to that observed when the wake is aligned with the leading edge.

When the wake flows across the suction side endwall, the coolant coverage areas from both slot suction side and pressure side decrease. This reduction occurs because the wake further reduces the pressure on the suction side endwall, facilitating coolant outflow from the slot in this region. However, the excessive high momentum of the coolant causes it to directly enter the mainstream, thereby shortening the axial coverage length on suction side endwall. The variation in slashface coolant coverage is minimal compared with uniform inflow, as the wake's influence zone is distributed near the regions with strong secondary vortices, including the suction side HV. The influence of the weak flow dissipates rapidly with the secondary vortices, making it difficult to affect downstream endwall regions.

FIGURE 5: Endwall cooling effectiveness distributions with different wake position

Fig. 6 presents the variation of laterally averaged endwall cooling effectiveness at different instants during wake passing. Overall, the slot ejection and its separation during downstream development result in a gradual decrease in cooling effectiveness in the $z < 0$ region as the axial coordinate increases. Under the coverage of axially distributed slashface jets, the region $0.1 < z/C_{ax} < 1.1$ maintains relatively high and uniform

cooling effectiveness. However, the endwall pressure and secondary flows cause non-uniform slashface jets, leading to certain fluctuations in the averaging cooling effectiveness distribution along the axial direction in this region.

When the wake is directly aligned with the leading edge, the average cooling effectiveness of the endwall is significantly higher than other conditions, with averaging cooling effectiveness reaching above 0.5. This corresponds to the substantial improvement in cooling effectiveness on the pressure side endwall shown in Fig. 5b, indicating that attention should be focused on the pressure side endwall region where coolant is difficult to reach when managing to improve the endwall cooling effectiveness. When the wake flow is aligned with cascade suction side, the endwall exhibits the worst averaging cooling performance, with averaging cooling effectiveness approximately 0.1-0.2 lower than when the wake is directly aligned with the pressure side.

When the wake flow is aligned with the pressure side and mid-pitch location, the averaging cooling effectiveness are relatively similar. However, in the region $0 < z/C_{ax} < 0.2$, the coolant coverage enlargement on pressure side endwall when the wake is aligned with the leading edge improves the average cooling effectiveness in this region by approximately 0.1. For both operating conditions in the region $0.5 < z/C_{ax} < 1.0$, the cooling effectiveness caused by slashface jets is comparable to that of the pressure side alignment condition, with average cooling effectiveness in this downstream region reaching 0.5-0.6. This indicates that during the movement of wake from leading edge to mid-pitch location, the coolant jets in the slashface downstream part are minimally affected.

FIGURE 6: Laterally averaging cooling effectiveness with different wake position

Fig. 7 presents the variation of averaging cooling effectiveness in five axial regions ($0 < z/C_{ax} < 20\%$, $20\% < z/C_{ax} < 40\%$, etc.) from upstream to downstream on the endwall during one pitch period of wake movement. As the wake moves from the pressure side to the suction side, the average cooling effectiveness in all five endwall regions exhibits a consistent variation trend. When the wake moves from the

leading edge toward the pressure side, the average endwall cooling effectiveness first decreases and then rapidly increases to its maximum value, reaching a peak average cooling effectiveness of 0.82. The most upstream region ($0 < z/C_{ax} < 20\%$) shows the largest fluctuation because when the wake is directly aligned with the region where slot outflow is difficult, the coolant outflow in this region increases rapidly. However, as the wake continues moving toward the suction side, the pressure side horseshoe vortex begins to restrict the expansion of slot coolant toward pressure side. Subsequently, as the wake continues moving toward the suction side, the average endwall cooling effectiveness gradually decreases. When the wake reaches upstream of the suction side ($t = T_0 + 80\% \tau$), the average endwall cooling effectiveness begins to increase gradually. This occurs because the suction side endwall is the region with the maximum slot coolant outflow, and when the wake moves to this region, the tendency for suction side slot coolant to directly separate from the endwall becomes more pronounced. Consequently, the average endwall cooling effectiveness is relatively low at this time, approximately 0.6.

FIGURE 7: Averaging cooling effectiveness variations of different endwall regions along with wake movement

Fig. 8 shows the slashface ingestion patterns along with coolant streamlines during different wake positions. Under typical conditions, slot coolant and part of the mainstream ingests strongly into the leading edge region of the slashface, which is also the primary cause of non-uniform slashface ejection and downstream coolant accumulation. When the wake is at different pitchwise positions, the slashface consistently exhibits the characteristic of weak upstream ejection and strong downstream ejection. Wake movement significantly affects the intensity of the two gap coolant jets, while simultaneously inducing periodic strong ingestion within the slashface.

When the wake flows across the pressure side, the ingestion intensity and depth in the middle part of the slashface reach their maximum during this phase. This is because the slot coolant

outflow on the pressure side is relatively large at this time. When the wake passes through the mid-pitch location, the static pressure barrier at the slashface interface is at its weakest, resulting in minimal slashface ingestion. Coolant from the slashface tends to enter the mainstream directly rather than reattaching on the endwall, leading to the smallest endwall coverage area as shown in Fig. 5. When the wake is aligned with the suction side, the upstream high-temperature region within the slashface has a relatively large area, indicating that mainstream ingestion into the slashface leading edge is most intense at this time. This is related to the rapid increase in slot coolant flow at this moment.

FIGURE 8: Ingestion and outflow patterns in slashface with different wake position

Figure 9 presents the variation of average outflow velocity across five axial regions ($0 < z/C_{ax} < 20\%$, $20\% < z/C_{ax} < 40\%$, etc.) from upstream to downstream at the slashface exit plane during one pitch period of wake migration.

The $0 < z/C_{ax} < 40\%$ region exhibits the lowest average outflow velocity among the five regions, with velocities ranging merely from 5-10 m/s. This region constitutes the primary zone where mainstream ingestion into the slashface occurs. When the upstream wake moves, the averaging velocity fluctuation in this region is approximately 3 m/s.

The $60\% < z/C_{ax} < 80\%$ region demonstrates the highest average outflow velocity, indicating that this region serves as the primary zone for coolant accumulation and subsequent outflow from the slashface. The lateral movement of the wake exerts the most significant influence on the outflow velocity in this region. When the wake is positioned at the mid-pitch location, the average outflow velocity reaches 20 m/s, whereas when the wake is located on pressure side or suction side, the average outflow velocity is only 15 m/s.

The $40\% < z/C_{ax} < 60\%$ and $80\% < z/C_{ax} < 100\%$ regions exhibit similar coolant outflow velocities for most of the time period. The $40\% < z/C_{ax} < 60\%$ region experiences a substantial enhancement in outflow when the wake is positioned on pressure side, while the $80\% < z/C_{ax} < 100\%$ region outflow remains nearly unaffected by the wake due to its considerable distance from the wake region.

FIGURE 9: Averaging outflow velocity variations of different slashface regions along with wake movement

Figure 10 presents the endwall limiting streamline distributions when the wake is positioned at four different characteristic locations. The pressure side HV migrates from the blade leading edge toward the suction side and traverses from the middle region of the slashface to suction side endwall. The suction side HV develops around the blade suction side surface and separates from the endwall near blade shoulder. The separation of slot coolant jets from the suction side endwall induces separation vortex (SV), which is located in close proximity to the suction side HV. Significant streamline ingestion phenomena can be observed at the slashface leading edge.

When the wake is aligned with blade leading edge, a distinctive difference from the other three conditions is observed: streamlines flow out from the pressure side slot rather than being dominated by the crossflow originating from blade leading edge. This phenomenon accounts for the protrusion in the pressure side slot coverage shown in Fig. 5(a). When the wake is aligned with the pressure side, the pressure side HV moves substantially downstream influenced by pressure side slot leakage, thereby achieving relatively favorable cooling effectiveness on the upstream pressure side endwall. Simultaneously, the downstream migration of the pressure side HV mitigates the ingestion at the leading edge region of the slashface, resulting in effective endwall coverage by the coolant from upstream part slashface as shown in Fig. 5(b). When the wake is aligned with the mid-pitch and suction side, the pressure side HV traverses the slashface from the $z/C_{ax}=0.5$, with virtually no slashface coolant outflow in the upstream region. This is attributed to the combined suppression by the slot coolant and HV, while the influence of the wake's low-pressure region cannot extend to the slashface location at this position.

FIGURE 10: Endwall limiting streamline distributions with different wake position

Figure 11 presents the 2D streamline distributions at the $z/C_{ax}=0.37$ cross-section when the wake is positioned at four different characteristic locations. At this location near the throat, the suction side HV dominates the flow above the suction side endwall, while the pressure side HV has developed to a position above the slashface, exerting certain influence on slashface coolant outflow. As illustrated in Fig. 11, the pitchwise position of the wake significantly affects the lateral development of the pressure side HV and its merger with the suction side secondary vortices.

When the wake is aligned with the leading edge and pressure side, the secondary flow exhibits a larger influencing extent. This occurs because the wake low-pressure region is located on pressure side, which weakens the lateral pressure gradient within the endwall region, thereby enabling the SV to influence a broader pressure side area while simultaneously reducing the migration velocity of the pressure side HV toward the suction side. When the wake is aligned with the mid-pitch location, the lateral pressure gradient in the endwall region from the blade pressure surface toward the wake region is substantial, and the suction side HV and SV can barely influence the pressure side endwall at this axial location. When the wake is aligned with the suction side, the lifting height of the suction side HV is significantly greater than in other conditions, which corresponds to the reduced coverage distance of slot coolant on suction side endwall as shown in Fig. 5(d). The primary reason

is that the wake blows the suction side HV away from the endwall by reducing the suction side pressure and increasing the suction side slot coolant ejection tendency.

FIGURE 11: 2D streamline and temperature distributions on cascade cross-section with different wake position

The total pressure loss coefficient (ξ) is defined as follows:

$$\xi = \frac{P_{\infty} - P}{P_{\infty}} \quad (8)$$

where P_{∞} represents the mainstream pressure, and P denotes the local total pressure.

Figure 12 presents the total pressure loss coefficient (ξ) distributions at the cascade exit cross-section when the wake is positioned at four different characteristic locations. The wake significantly affects the aerodynamic losses in the cascade endwall region by influencing the lateral pressure gradient in the endwall region and the secondary flow development.

When the wake is aligned with the leading edge and pressure side, corresponding to the larger secondary flow extent shown in Fig. 11, the passage vortex loss at the cascade exit is larger. When the wake is aligned with the suction side, the secondary flow is located closer to the suction side, and the coolant ejection from the middle region of the slashface is stronger. Consequently, the secondary flow forms the passage vortex more rapidly, and the passage vortex exhibits a larger influence range at the cascade exit.

FIGURE 12: Pressure loss coefficient distributions on cascade exit with different wake position

Figure 13 presents the variation of averaging total pressure loss coefficient at the cascade exit plane during one pitch period of wake migration. When the wake is aligned with the leading edge and pressure side, the pressure losses are greater, which is consistent with the larger secondary flow influence range shown in Fig. 11. When the upstream wake is positioned at the leading edge location near the pressure side ($t=T_0+8\% \tau$), the averaging total pressure loss at the cascade exit reaches its maximum. Subsequently, the pressure loss gradually decreases with wake migration, reaching its minimum when the wake is positioned near the mid-pitch location ($t=T_0+40\% \tau$).

FIGURE 13: Averaging pressure loss coefficient variations on cascade exit along with wake movement

4. CONCLUSION

In response to the sweeping of vane wake causing periodic film cooling failure on turbine endwall and increased risk of gap ingestion, this study employs unsteady RANS method to numerically investigate the variations in slashface and slot coolant non-uniform outflow and ingestion patterns with wake movement. The unsteady mixing characteristics between endwall multi-gap coolant jets and secondary vortices, as well as endwall cooling performance are analyzed.

When the wake is aligned with the leading edge, the pressure side slot ejection is strengthened and forms a protruding coverage on endwall, while the low-pressure region of wake flow on pressure side weakens the lateral pressure gradient within the endwall region. When the wake sweeps across the cascade pressure side, the cooling effectiveness of the pressure side endwall is substantially enhanced. The increased pressure side slot ejection results in the most severe ingestion at the middle part of the slashface, but the slashface coolant exhibits the most uniform axial attachment to the endwall. When the wake is aligned with the mid-pitch location, the coverage length of slot coolant on suction side endwall increases, and the influence of the suction

side horseshoe vortex on pressure side endwall is minimized. When the wake is aligned with the suction side, the low-pressure region of wake flow further deteriorates the reattachment effect of the suction side slot coolant, resulting in an average endwall cooling effectiveness approximately 0.1-0.2 lower than when the wake is aligned with the pressure side. And the increased slot ejection causes the most severe ingestion at the slashface leading edge.

During one periodic migration of the wake from the blade leading edge toward the suction side, the averaging endwall cooling effectiveness reaches relatively high values when the wake is aligned with leading edge and pressure side, then gradually decreases during the movement toward suction side. The slashface region between $60\% < z/C_{ax} < 80\%$ exhibits the highest average outflow velocity and is most significantly affected by the outflow velocity fluctuations caused by wake migration. The total pressure loss coefficient at the exit first decreases and then increases, reaching its minimum value when the wake is aligned with the mid-pitch location.

Therefore, as the upstream wake sweeping position changes, significant variations would occur in slashface ingestion range and endwall cooling coverage compared with the ideal uniform inflow condition. Advanced endwall cooling layout designs should consider the typical turbine unsteady effects such as wake flow to enhance turbine cooling performance robustness.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Bunker R S. A review of shaped hole turbine film-cooling technology[J]. *J. Heat Transfer*, 2005, 127(4): 441-453.
- [2] Du K, Liu Y, Luo D, et al. Improved prediction of film cooling effectiveness for flat-surface film holes in gas turbine endwalls and blades by considering turbulent Schmidt number modeling[J]. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 2025: 127881.
- [3] Zhang J, Zhang S. Recent advances in film cooling enhancement: A review[J]. *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 2020, 33(4): 1119-1136.
- [4] Ahn J. Large eddy simulation of film cooling: A review[J]. *Energies*, 15(23): 8876, 2022.
- [5] Qenawy M, Taha M, Elbatran A H A. Unsteady adiabatic film cooling effectiveness behind shaped holes[J]. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 2022, 34: 102005.
- [6] Choi S M, Kim J, Bang M, et al. Effect of the wake on the heat transfer of a turbine blade endwall according to relative position of the cylindrical rod[J]. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 2018, 94: 61-70.
- [7] Yang X, Feng Z, Simon T W. Steady and unsteady RANS simulations of heat transfer on a turbine vane endwall with inlet boundary layer skew[C]//13 th European Conference

on Turbomachinery Fluid dynamics & Thermodynamics. EUROPEAN TURBOMACHINERY SOCIETY, 2019.

[8] Zhang L, Moon H K. Turbine nozzle endwall inlet film cooling: the effect of a back-facing step[C]//Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air. 2003, 36886: 203-211.

[9] Zhou W, Pu J, Wang J, et al. Experimental investigation of hole-geometry effect on unsteady characteristics of film cooling at turbine vane leading edge[J]. International Journal of Thermal Sciences, 2022, 179: 107715.

[10] Fawcett R J, Wheeler A P S, He L, et al. Experimental investigation into the impact of crossflow on the coherent unsteadiness within film cooling flows[J]. International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow, 2013, 40: 32-42.

[11] Cardwell N D, Sundaram N, Thole K A. Effect of midpassage gap, endwall misalignment, and roughness on endwall film-cooling[J]. J. Turbomach., 128(1): 62-70, 2006.

[12] Brack S, Muller Y. Probabilistic analysis of the secondary air system of a low-pressure turbine[J]. Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power, 2015, 137(2): 022602.

[13] Zhang J, Liu C, Niu X, et al. Effect of upstream leakage flow on film cooling characteristic of a turbine convex endwall[J]. Journal of Turbomachinery, 2023, 145(11).

[14] Feng M, Dai X, Zhang F, et al. Numerical investigation on film cooling and aerodynamic performance for gas turbine endwalls with upstream vane-type and cascade-type slots[J]. Aerospace Science and Technology, 2024, 145: 108857.

[15] Shaikh F, Rosic B. Aerodynamics and heat transfer inside a gas turbine mid-passage gap[J]. Journal of Turbomachinery, 2022, 144(4): 041010.

[16] Zhang K, Li Z, Shao W, et al. Numerical Analysis of Leakage Flow and Film Cooling Characteristics of the Inclined Slashface on Gas Turbine Endwall[J]. Journal of Thermal Science and Engineering Applications, 2025, 17(7): 071005.

[17] Julien S, Lefrancois J, Dumas G, et al. Simulations of flow ingestion and related structures in a turbine disk cavity[C]. ASME Turbo Expo, GT2010-22729, 2010.

[18] Lin A, Liu G, Yu X, et al. Comprehensive investigations on fluid flow and heat transfer characteristics of a

high-speed rotating turbine disk cavity system of aero-engine[J]. International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer, 2022, 136: 106170.

[19] Beaux J H, Girardeau J, Khelladi S, et al. Numerical Investigations of Flows and Heat Transfer in Turbine Disk Cavities[J]. Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power, 2024, 146(10).

[20] Du Q, Xu G, Xu Q, et al. Detached eddy simulation of the unsteady flow and film cooling characteristics of an endwall with an interrupted slot[J]. Journal of Turbomachinery, 2022, 144(10): 101012.

[21] Lopes G, Lavagnoli S. Unsteadiness in the Secondary Flows of a High-Speed Low-Pressure Turbine Cascade With Unsteady Wakes and Purge Flow[J]. Journal of Turbomachinery, 2025, 147(9): 091017.

[22] Liu Y, Luo Y. Transient simulation of pulsed purge film cooling on flow and thermal characteristics of a turbine endwall[J]. Applied Thermal Engineering, 2019, 161: 114208.

[23] Chowdhury N H K, Shiau C C, Han J C, et al. Turbine vane endwall film cooling with slashface leakage and discrete hole configuration[J]. J. Turbomach., 139(6): 061003, 2017.

[24] Park J S, Jung E Y, Lee D H, et al. Effects of unsteady wake on heat transfer of endwall surface in linear cascade[J]. Journal of heat transfer, 2014, 136(6): 061701.

[25] Chen L, Lu Z F, Dai R. Unsteady effects of upstream nozzle wakes on hub-endwall flow and heat transfer of an HPT rotor[J]. Journal of Applied Fluid Mechanics, 2020, 13(2): 513-526.

[27] Chen A F, Shiau C C, and Han J C, Turbine Blade Platform Film Cooling with Simulated Swirl Purge Flow and Slashface Leakage Conditions, ASME J. Turbomach., 139(3): 031012, 2017.

[26] El-Gabry L A, Ameri A A. Comparison of steady and unsteady RANS heat transfer simulations of hub and endwall of a turbine blade passage[J]. J. Turbomach. 133(3): 031010, 2011.